

THE INFLUENCE OF GOAL ORIENTATION, FEEDBACK ORIENTATION, AND WORK ENVIRONMENT ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE AT PT MASABARU GUNAPERSADA IN SURABAYA

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the effects of Goal Orientation, Feedback Orientation, and Work Environment on employee performance at PT. Masabaru Gunapersada in Surabaya. The research employs a quantitative method with an associative approach. The population of this study consists of all employees of PT. Masabaru Gunapersada in Surabaya, totaling 56 employees, and the entire population is used as the research sample through a census sampling technique. Data collection was conducted by distributing questionnaires using a Likert scale. The data analysis techniques include data quality testing, classical assumption tests, multiple linear regression analysis, partial tests, simultaneous tests, and coefficient of determination analysis, with the assistance of SPSS software. The results show that Goal Orientation and Work Environment partially have a significant effect on employee performance, while Feedback Orientation partially does not have a significant effect on employee performance. Simultaneously, Goal Orientation, Feedback Orientation, and Work Environment have a significant effect on employee performance, with Work Environment being the most dominant variable influencing employee performance at PT. Masabaru Gunapersada in Surabaya.

Keywords: Employee Performance, Feedback Orientation, Goal Orientation, Work Environment

INTRODUCTION

In the current era of globalization and increasingly intense business competition, companies are required to continuously innovate and improve performance in order to survive and grow. One of the primary ways to achieve this is by enhancing employee performance. Optimal employee performance has a direct impact on organizational success in addressing business challenges, particularly in terms of productivity, efficiency, and the quality of services or products delivered. Strong employee performance supports the achievement of organizational objectives and provides a competitive advantage in an increasingly competitive market. PT Masabaru Gunapersada, located in Surabaya, is a leading logistics and supply chain company engaged in the trading and distribution of off-the-road tires and rims, trailer components for mining, forestry, and agriculture, port operations, and on-road applications, supported by an extensive network of bonded warehouses, transportation facilities, and VHS. As a growing company, PT Masabaru Gunapersada faces the challenge of continuously improving employee performance in order to maintain competitiveness and achieve its organizational goals. Therefore, the company needs to focus on factors that can enhance employee performance, particularly by understanding how goal orientation, feedback orientation, and the work environment influence employee performance.

Goal orientation is one of the important factors influencing employee performance. Goal orientation refers to an individual's tendency to engage in tasks or work activities with a focus on achieving specific goals (Rahman et al., 2024). More specifically, goal orientation distinguishes individuals based on the types of goals they pursue, such as goals aimed at mastering new skills (learning goal orientation) or goals focused on demonstrating competence and achievement (performance goal orientation). At PT Masabaru Gunapersada, the application of goal orientation is expected to encourage employees to develop clearer orientations toward achieving both personal and organizational goals, thereby enhancing their performance. Previous studies by Rahman et al. (2024) and Hasbullah (2022) have found that goal orientation has a significant effect on employee performance. Employees with clear goal orientation tend to be more motivated and focused in achieving targets, which ultimately leads to significant

performance improvements. In addition, feedback orientation is another important factor that affects employee performance. Feedback orientation refers to an individual's attitude and readiness to receive and utilize feedback to improve performance (Fajar et al., 2021). Employees with high feedback orientation tend to be more open to criticism and suggestions and use feedback as a tool for self-improvement. At PT Masabaru Gunapersada, the effective implementation of feedback is crucial for enhancing employee work quality. Research by Fajar et al. (2021) and Hasbullah (2022) indicates that feedback orientation has a significant effect on employee performance. Employees who actively seek feedback and use it to improve their performance tend to demonstrate higher levels of achievement. The work environment is also a critical factor influencing employee performance. The work environment refers to the physical, social, and psychological conditions in the workplace that can affect employee comfort and productivity. A supportive work environment can enhance employee motivation and morale, whereas an unsupportive environment may reduce performance. At PT Masabaru Gunapersada, physical conditions such as adequate facilities, positive interpersonal relationships among employees, and supervisory support play an important role in creating a conducive work environment. Studies by Pratiwi et al. (2025) and Daraizqy et al. (2025) show that the work environment has a significant effect on employee performance. A supportive work environment enables employees to work more effectively and efficiently and motivates them to achieve organizational goals.

This study offers novelty by integrating three important variables, goal orientation, feedback orientation, and work environment into a single framework to examine their effects on employee performance at PT Masabaru Gunapersada. Although many previous studies have examined the relationships between these variables individually, this research provides new insights into the interaction among these factors within a specific organizational context. This study is important because it offers clearer guidance for PT Masabaru Gunapersada in managing employee performance by focusing on factors that directly influence productivity and work quality. Furthermore, the findings of this study may serve as a reference for other companies facing similar challenges in improving employee performance amid intense business competition.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Goal Orientation

Goal orientation refers to the reasons or purposes underlying why an individual engages in a particular task (Dweck & Leggett, as cited in Fajar et al., 2025). It is a psychological construct that describes how individuals respond to, react to, and interpret situations in their efforts to achieve specific goals (Rahman et al., 2024).

Feedback Orientation

Feedback orientation refers to individual differences that reflect a person's unique characteristics in responding to and receiving feedback as a whole (Linderbaum & Levy, as cited in Fajar et al., 2025). One of the main aspects of feedback orientation is feedback utility. Utility refers to an individual's tendency to believe that feedback is useful for achieving goals or obtaining desired outcomes (Linderbaum & Levy, as cited in Fajar et al., 2025).

Work Environment

According to Farida and Hartono, as cited in Daraizqy et al. (2025), the work environment refers to workplace conditions that encompass both physical and non-physical elements, creating a pleasant, calm, and comfortable atmosphere that fosters a sense of well-being among employees. Meanwhile, Sedarmayanti, as cited in Ayuni and Vidada (2024), defines the work environment as the overall conditions that include work equipment, materials used, and the surrounding environment in which individuals perform their jobs.

Employee Performance

According to Colquitt, as cited in Fajar et al. (2021), performance is formally defined as the value of employees' behaviors that contribute to the achievement of organizational goals. Meanwhile, Mardiyanti, as cited in Fajar et al. (2021), states that performance refers to work outcomes encompassing both the quality and quantity achieved by employees in carrying out the tasks assigned to them.

METHOD

This study investigates the effect of goal orientation, feedback orientation, and work environment on employee performance at PT Masabaru Gunapersada, Surabaya. The research was conducted at the company's headquarters in Surabaya and involved all 56 employees as respondents, using a census sampling technique due to the relatively small population size. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire based on established theoretical

constructs and indicators for each variable. The variables examined consist of goal orientation, feedback orientation, and work environment as independent variables, and employee performance as the dependent variable. Measurement was carried out using a five-point Likert scale to capture employees' perceptions, attitudes, and experiences related to the studied variables. Data analysis employed quantitative methods using SPSS software. The analytical procedures included data quality tests (validity and reliability), multiple linear regression analysis, partial tests (t-test), simultaneous tests (F-test), and the coefficient of determination (R^2).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validity Test Result

The purpose of the validity test in this study is to ensure that each statement item in the research instrument accurately measures the variables of goal orientation, feedback orientation, work environment, and employee performance in accordance with the intended research concepts. Validity was assessed by examining the correlation between each item score and the total variable score. An item is considered valid if the calculated correlation coefficient (r-value) exceeds the critical value (r-table) at a 5% significance level. The results of the validity test in this study are as follows:

Table 1. Validity Test Results

No	Variable	r-count	r-table	Result
1	Goal Orientation Item 1	0,753	0,263	Valid
2	Goal Orientation Item 2	0,702	0,263	Valid
3	Goal Orientation Item 3	0,637	0,263	Valid
4	Feedback Orientation Item 1	0,273	0,263	Valid
5	Feedback Orientation Item 2	0,654	0,263	Valid
6	Feedback Orientation Item 3	0,710	0,263	Valid
7	Feedback Orientation Item 4	0,742	0,263	Valid
8	Work Environment Item 1	0,599	0,263	Valid
9	Work Environment Item 2	0,699	0,263	Valid
10	Work Environment Item 3	0,572	0,263	Valid
11	Work Environment Item 4	0,579	0,263	Valid
12	Employee Performance Item 1	0,750	0,263	Valid
13	Employee Performance Item 2	0,637	0,263	Valid
14	Employee Performance Item 3	0,705	0,263	Valid

The validity test results indicate that all questionnaire items for the variables of goal orientation, feedback orientation, work environment, and employee performance have r-values greater than the r-table value of 0.263. This finding demonstrates an adequate correlation between each item score and the total score of the measured variable. Therefore, all questionnaire items are declared valid and appropriate for use in this study.

Reliability Test Results

The reliability test in this study aims to assess the consistency and stability of the research instrument in measuring goal orientation, feedback orientation, work environment, and employee performance. Reliability was evaluated to ensure that the questionnaire items produce consistent results when administered at different times or under similar conditions. The instrument is considered reliable if the Cronbach's Alpha value exceeds 0.70. The results of the reliability test in this study are as follows:

Table 2. Reliability Test Results

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.786	14

The results of the reliability test show that the obtained Cronbach's Alpha value is 0.786, which exceeds the minimum threshold of 0.70. This finding indicates that the research instrument has good internal consistency in measuring the variables of goal orientation, feedback orientation, work environment, and employee performance. Therefore, all questionnaire items are considered reliable.

Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression analysis is conducted to determine the magnitude of the contribution of each independent variable, both partially and simultaneously. In this study, the multiple linear regression model is used to examine the effect of goal orientation (X_1), feedback orientation (X_2), and work environment (X_3) on employee performance (Y). The results of the multiple linear regression analysis are presented as follows:

Table 3. Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	-.775	1.126		-.688	.494
Goal Orientation	.185	.083	.185	2.233	.030
Feedback Orientation	.039	.051	.050	.763	.449
Work Environment	.625	.073	.742	8.564	.000

Based on the table above, the multiple linear regression equation obtained in this study is as follows:

$$Y = -0,775 + 0,185X_1 + 0,039X_2 + 0,625X_3$$

- Y = Employee performance
- X_1 = Goal Orientation
- X_2 = Feedback Orientation
- X_3 = Work Environment

The interpretation of the regression equation can be explained as follows:

1. The constant value of -0.775 indicates that when goal orientation, feedback orientation, and work environment are equal to zero, employee performance is at -0.775 . This value represents the baseline level of employee performance before being influenced by the independent variables.
2. The regression coefficient of goal orientation (X_1) is 0.185 , indicating that a one-unit increase in goal orientation will lead to an increase in employee performance of 0.185 units, assuming the other independent variables remain constant. Conversely, a one-unit decrease in goal orientation will result in a decrease in employee performance by 0.185 units.
3. The regression coefficient of feedback orientation (X_2) is 0.039 , indicating that each one-unit increase in feedback orientation will increase employee performance by 0.039 units, assuming the other independent variables remain constant. Conversely, a one-unit decrease in feedback orientation will reduce employee performance by 0.039 units.
4. The regression coefficient of work environment (X_3) is 0.625 , indicating that a one-unit increase in the work environment variable will increase employee performance by 0.625 units, assuming the other independent variables remain unchanged. Conversely, a one-unit decrease in the work environment will result in a decrease in employee performance by 0.625 units.

Results of the Partial Test

The partial test (t-test) is used to examine the individual effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable. In this study, the t-test aims to determine whether goal orientation, feedback orientation, and work environment individually have a significant effect on employee performance at PT. Masabaru Gunapersada in Surabaya, while controlling for the influence of the other independent variables in the regression model. Based on Table 3, the decisions of the partial test results in this study are as follows:

1. The goal orientation variable has a significance value of 0.030 , which is lower than 0.05 . This result indicates that goal orientation has a significant effect on employee performance.
2. The feedback orientation variable has a significance value of 0.449 , which is greater than 0.05 . This finding indicates that feedback orientation does not have a significant effect on employee performance.
3. The work environment variable has a significance value of 0.000 , which is lower than 0.05 . This result indicates that the work environment has a significant effect on employee performance. In addition, the work environment variable has the highest standardized coefficient (Beta) value of 8.564 compared to goal orientation and feedback orientation. This finding shows that the work environment has the strongest influence

on employee performance among the independent variables in the regression model. Therefore, the work environment can be identified as the most dominant variable affecting employee performance at PT. Masabaru Gunapersada in Surabaya.

Results of the Simultaneous Test

The purpose of the simultaneous test in this study is to examine the joint effect of goal orientation, feedback orientation, and work environment on employee performance at PT. Masabaru Gunapersada in Surabaya. The simultaneous test is conducted to assess whether all independent variables included in the regression model collectively have a significant effect on the dependent variable. Through this test, it can be determined whether the regression model is capable of explaining variations in employee performance based on the combined influence of goal orientation, feedback orientation, and work environment. The results of the simultaneous test are presented as follows:

Table 4. Results of the Simultaneous Test

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	46.264	3	15.421	71.031	.000 ^b
Residual	11.290	52	.217		
Total	57.554	55			

The interpretation of the simultaneous test results is based on a significance value of 0.000 at a 0.05 significance level. Since the significance value is lower than 0.05, it can be concluded that goal orientation, feedback orientation, and work environment simultaneously have a significant effect on employee performance.

Results of the Coefficient of Determination Test

The coefficient of determination test aims to assess how well goal orientation, feedback orientation, and work environment explain variations in employee performance at PT. Masabaru Gunapersada in Surabaya by measuring the proportion of variance in the dependent variable explained by the regression model. The results of the coefficient of determination test are presented as follows:

Table 5. Results of the Coefficient of Determination Test

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.897 ^a	.804	.793	.46595

The results indicate that the R Square value is 0.804, which is equivalent to 80.4%. This finding shows that goal orientation, feedback orientation, and work environment are able to explain 80.4% of the variation in employee performance. Meanwhile, the remaining 19.6% of the variation in employee performance is influenced by other variables outside the research model that were not examined in this study. These results suggest that the regression model used has a high explanatory power in explaining changes in employee performance.

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Goal Orientation on Employee Performance

Based on the results of the partial test, the goal orientation variable has a significance value of 0.030, which is lower than the significance level of 0.05. This result indicates that goal orientation has a significant effect on employee performance at PT. Masabaru Gunapersada in Surabaya. Theoretically, goal orientation refers to an individual’s tendency to set, pursue, and interpret work-related goals. Rahman et al. (2024) explain that goal orientation reflects an individual’s orientation toward goal achievement, whether focused on mastering abilities or attaining work outcomes. Hasbullah (2022) states that employees with clear goal orientation tend to have more structured work direction, higher levels of motivation, and greater commitment to completing tasks in accordance with predetermined targets. The reason why goal orientation has a significant effect on employee performance in this study can be explained by the actual conditions at PT. Masabaru Gunapersada in Surabaya, which operates in the transportation, logistics, and supply chain management sector with a high level of competition. The company’s operational activities require punctuality, accuracy, and consistent achievement of distribution targets. Under these

conditions, employees with strong goal orientation are more focused on achieving work targets, better able to manage time and responsibilities effectively, and demonstrate higher commitment to organizational goals, resulting in more optimal performance. The regression coefficient value for goal orientation of 0.185 indicates a positive relationship between goal orientation and employee performance. This value suggests that every one-unit increase in goal orientation is followed by an increase in employee performance of 0.185 units, assuming other variables remain constant. This positive relationship reflects that the clearer the work goals possessed by employees at PT. Masabaru Gunapersada in Surabaya, the better the performance demonstrated in carrying out daily tasks, particularly in supporting the smooth distribution and logistics services of the company

The Effect of Feedback Orientation on Employee Performance

Based on the results of the partial test, the feedback orientation variable has a significance value of 0.449, which is higher than the significance level of 0.05. This result indicates that feedback orientation does not have a significant effect on employee performance at PT. Masabaru Gunapersada in Surabaya. Theoretically, feedback orientation is defined as an individual's attitude, readiness, and tendency to receive, seek, and utilize feedback to improve work behavior and outcomes. Fajar et al. (2021) explain that feedback orientation reflects the extent to which employees perceive feedback as a means of learning and self-development. Hasbullah (2022) states that individuals with high feedback orientation tend to be more open to evaluation and able to use the feedback provided to enhance the quality of their performance.

The reason why feedback orientation does not have a significant effect on employee performance in this study can be explained by the actual conditions at PT. Masabaru Gunapersada in Surabaya. As a company operating in the transportation and logistics sector, work patterns tend to be strongly oriented toward operational targets, punctuality, and standardized work procedures. Under these conditions, employees rely more on established operational standards and direct instructions from supervisors than on continuous feedback processing. In addition, the feedback received by employees is largely administrative and technical in nature, and therefore has not been fully utilized as a reflective tool for improving individual performance.

The regression coefficient value for feedback orientation is 0.039, indicating a positive relationship between feedback orientation and employee performance, but with a relatively small effect. This value suggests that increases in feedback orientation are followed by only marginal improvements in employee performance. This condition indicates that although employees may be ready to receive feedback, feedback orientation has not become a primary driver of performance improvement at PT. Masabaru Gunapersada in Surabaya compared to other factors such as goal clarity and the work environment.

The Effect of Work Environment on Employee Performance

Based on the results of the partial test, the work environment variable has a significance value of 0.000, which is lower than the significance level of 0.05. This result indicates that the work environment has a significant effect on employee performance at PT. Masabaru Gunapersada in Surabaya. Conceptually, the work environment refers to the overall physical, social, and psychological conditions surrounding employees in carrying out their work activities. Pratiwi et al. (2025) explain that the work environment includes aspects such as work facilities, relationships among employees, communication patterns, and leadership support, all of which can influence employee comfort and productivity. Daraizqy et al. (2025) state that a supportive work environment creates a sense of safety and comfort for employees, enabling them to work optimally and consistently.

The reason why the work environment has a significant effect on employee performance in this study is consistent with the actual conditions at PT. Masabaru Gunapersada in Surabaya, which operates in the transportation, logistics, and supply chain management sector. The company's operational activities require intensive coordination, punctuality, and strong cooperation across departments. A work environment supported by adequate facilities, clear work systems, and harmonious relationships between supervisors and employees plays a crucial role in ensuring smooth operations. Such conditions allow employees to work with greater focus, comfort, and responsibility, resulting in improved performance. The regression coefficient value for the work environment variable is 0.625, indicating a strong positive relationship between the work environment and employee performance. This value suggests that a one-unit increase in the work environment will lead to an increase in employee performance of 0.625 units, assuming other variables remain constant. In addition, the standardized coefficient (Beta) value of 0.742 is the highest among the independent variables, indicating that the work environment has the most dominant influence on employee performance at PT. Masabaru Gunapersada in Surabaya. This finding highlights that work environment conditions are the primary factor driving improvements in employee performance within the company.

The Effect of Goal Orientation, Feedback Orientation, and Work Environment on Employee Performance

Based on the results of the simultaneous test, the significance value obtained is 0.000, which is lower than the significance level of 0.05. This result indicates that goal orientation, feedback orientation, and work environment simultaneously have a significant effect on employee performance at PT. Masabaru Gunapersada in Surabaya. The simultaneous influence of these three independent variables reflects that employee performance is not determined by a single factor in isolation, but rather results from a combination of employees' goal orientation, their attitudes toward feedback, and the work environment that surrounds their daily work activities. At PT. Masabaru Gunapersada in Surabaya, employees are required to work in a goal-directed manner, be responsive to managerial direction, and adapt to a dynamic work environment. Therefore, the presence of goal orientation, feedback orientation, and work environment simultaneously shapes work patterns that support the achievement of optimal performance.

The results of the coefficient of determination test show an R Square value of 0.804, or 80.4%. This value indicates that 80.4% of the variation in employee performance at PT. Masabaru Gunapersada in Surabaya can be explained by the variables of goal orientation, feedback orientation, and work environment. Meanwhile, the remaining 19.6% of performance variation is influenced by other factors outside the research model, such as individual characteristics, leadership style, compensation systems, and other organizational factors that were not examined in this study. The relatively high coefficient of determination indicates that the regression model used has strong explanatory power in explaining changes in employee performance. This finding suggests that the combination of goal orientation, feedback orientation, and work environment plays a substantial role in shaping employee performance at PT. Masabaru Gunapersada in Surabaya. Accordingly, efforts to improve employee performance should be implemented in an integrated manner through the establishment of clear work goals, effective management of feedback aligned with organizational needs, and the creation of a supportive work environment that enhances both operational effectiveness and employee comfort

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Goal orientation has a significant partial effect on employee performance at PT. Masabaru Gunapersada in Surabaya. The positive regression coefficient indicates that an increase in goal orientation is followed by an improvement in employee performance. This finding is consistent with the actual conditions at PT. Masabaru Gunapersada, where operational activities require employees to work based on clear targets, punctuality, and the achievement of well-defined work objectives. Employees with strong goal orientation tend to be more focused, directed, and responsible in carrying out their tasks, resulting in more optimal performance.
2. Feedback orientation does not have a significant partial effect on employee performance at PT. Masabaru Gunapersada in Surabaya. Although the regression coefficient indicates a positive relationship, the effect is relatively weak and insufficient to drive significant performance improvement. This finding can be explained by the organizational context of PT. Masabaru Gunapersada, where the work system places greater emphasis on adherence to operational procedures and target achievement. The feedback received by employees is primarily technical and administrative in nature and has not been fully utilized as a mechanism for individual performance improvement.
3. Work environment has a significant partial effect on employee performance at PT. Masabaru Gunapersada in Surabaya and exhibits the largest positive regression coefficient among the examined variables. This result indicates that the work environment is the most dominant factor influencing employee performance. Working conditions, including adequate facilities, positive interpersonal relationships, supervisory support, and clear work systems, play a crucial role in supporting the company's operational activities. A supportive work environment enables employees to work more comfortably, focus better, and perform more efficiently, thereby enhancing overall performance.
4. Goal orientation, feedback orientation, and work environment simultaneously have a significant effect on employee performance at PT. Masabaru Gunapersada in Surabaya. The coefficient of determination results indicate that most of the variation in employee performance can be explained by these three variables, while the remaining variation is influenced by other factors outside the scope of this study. These findings suggest that employee performance at PT. Masabaru Gunapersada is shaped by a combination of goal orientation, feedback orientation, and work environment, with the work environment exerting the strongest influence among the variables examined.

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